

Different hot streaks for twin peaks in academic careers

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Abstract

Science to date has always been delivered by the unfettered imaginative insights of scientists. Curiously, many of these insights have derived from hot streaks for each scientist, but the evidence for why they happen is yet scarce. This paper approaches the problem from the view of team science. We firstly show that a hot streak has twin peaks; the former is early in a career, leading ideas as the first author, and the latter is late in a career, with supportive contributions as collaborators. Furthermore, the latter hot streak is characterized by larger teams but focused topics, which indicates the concentration strategy even in one's old age. These results drive valuable insights into the creative ecosystem in science, providing the essence of practical science support for any status of scientists.

Introduction

Hot streaks are one of the notable features of researchers' careers. Art, culture, and science all have hot streaks, and determining their intensity is important for quantifying the patterns governing the creative life cycle as well as discovering hidden talents (Liu et.al. 2018). Exploration and exploitation have a particularly strong relationship with hot streaks, and focusing on a single problem based on broad findings is important for creativity (Liu et.al. 2021). However, predicting hot streaks remains challenging due to the complexities of creative careers. Researchers make new discoveries serendipitously (Copeland 2019), which makes understanding what supports their success difficult.

Although numerous factors influence career success, team science represents one of the most dominant components. Connections with top researchers (Li et.al. 2019), as well as team size (Wu et.al. 2019), are influential factors in research topic selection and scientific contribution. Related to the repetition patterns of collaborations, co-authorship on single or multiple topics demonstrates a researcher's commitment to being both impactful and productive (Zeng et.al. 2022). In other words, funding, grants, and conference management could help researchers increase their creativity by promoting specific types of collaborations. Researchers have been connecting with other researchers in the lab, at conferences, and occasionally online, resulting in creative outcomes through the emergence of new intellectual innovations. As of now, it is unclear whether the team science trend is related to hot streaks.

To address this issue, we examined the hot streak timing and the co-authorship patterns of 5,253 researchers who have hot streaks to identify the predominated collaboration patterns. There are two research questions to be solved. Firstly, we clarify when a hot streak frequently occurs in a scientist's career because collaboration patterns are quite different depending on the status of scientists. Second, we show whether there is any difference in collaboration patterns between those who have experienced hot streaks and those who have not. This study is still in progress, so some results will be discussed in more detail.

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Materials and methods

We applied in-house comprehensive metadata of around 78 million papers in 1970-2022 from the Scopus custom dataset provided by Elsevier to analyze the publication history and collaboration patterns for each paper. The method consists of two steps. We first extracted researchers who had sufficiently long careers with hot streak moments, then compared the collaboration patterns with those who did not experience any hot streaks in their careers.

As a hot streak is characterized by the most prestigious discoveries of a career clustered in a short period, a hot streak is inevitable if fewer papers are submitted. Hence, we extracted 207,613 authors who published more than 80 papers and 20 years of their whole careers and then randomly selected 100,000 authors for the sake of computation runtime.

Next, scientists with a hot streak are defined as those whose top three impacts(cited) papers are concentrated within ten publications since the average duration of a hot streak is 3.7 years (Liu et.al. 2018) and average scientists publish nearly 2-3 publications per year. Beginning of hot streak t_H is defined as the time any of the top three impacts papers was published and lasts for ten publications during $t_H \sim t_H+10$. The impact of the paper is calculated from normalized 10-year citations by the average number of citations published in the same year and same category (Radicchi et.al. 2008). In previous research, hot streaks have been observed both in the absolute number of citations over a certain period and in terms of the collective impact on all papers submitted by the researchers (Liu et.al. 2018). In this study, we assume that the collaboration pattern with the co-authors has an impact on the impact of the output paper by influencing the researcher's imagination. Hence, we define the hot streak by absolute impact, not by collective impact. This method successfully collected the hot streak timing since the topic transition from exploration to exploitation, which is unique to the hot streak phenomenon (Liu et.al. 2021), has been observed for absolute impact hot streaks (Appendix).

Results

Of 100,000 target authors, 5,253 individuals experienced a single hot streak. The first finding is that the absolute impact hot streak has twin peaks; the former is the very first in their career, and the latter is just before the end of the career (Fig.1: Left). This is surprising because although the superiority of early performance is reasonable with survivorship bias in academia (Li et.al. 2020), the latter peak is not reported in previous work. Why could this happen? One characteristic of the latter hot streak is the supportive contribution as collaborators, not as 1st and last authors (Fig.1: Right). In other words, hot streaks follow different dynamics depending on the career stage of scientists; the early one is as a lead author providing the main idea of novel research, albeit the latter one is as a facilitator to enhance the team impact. Considering these findings prompted us to explore the significance of team science patterns in hot streaks.

We define the early and the late hot streak by selecting the first and the last 20% of 5,253 individuals who have experienced hot streaks. Team size, the number of authors of the paper, in the late hot streak is larger than the one in the early hot streak (Fig.2: Left). The papers published in the early hot streak are written by 3.2 authors on average, while in the late one the average is 6.7. For comparison, we randomly sample 1,000 authors without hot streaks each in the early and the late periods and randomly select ten consecutive publications in the periods.

They have larger average team sizes of 6.2 in the late than in the early of 4.3, but the difference is significant for authors with hot streaks. When scientists are junior, hot streaks, i.e., the brightest works, are more likely to occur in smaller teams; when older, hot streaks occur in larger teams. This trend is significantly more pronounced for scientists with hot streaks. Team

dynamics are distinctive when the brightest works in the career are produced and differ between the early and the late. Forming teams with many people whose interests are common in focused topics may be a key to producing hot streaks in the later periods.

Figure 1. Left: The average timing of the top 3 impact publications for 5,253 authors experiencing hot streaks. N^*/N represents the relative number of publications in a career. In a sequence of N works by an individual, N^* is the position of the first of top three impact work within a career. Right: Collaboration patterns of top 3 papers during hot streaks corresponding to the left figure.

Next, we characterize the number of topics during hot streak. This metric is the number of unique elements from the topics of the ten papers in a hot streak, thus ranging from 1 to 10. Topics are designated by co-citation network clustering of individual publications (Appendix). A small value can be interpreted as concentrating on a specific research topic, while a large value shows that researchers are working on various research topics. We observe that the average number of topics is smaller for those with hot streaks in both the early and the late (Fig. 2: Right). For authors with hot streaks, the average number of topics in the late is 4.2, smaller than the 4.8 in the early. For authors without hot streaks, also smaller in the late at 4.7 while 6.1 in the early. Scientists with hot streaks concentrate on relatively few topics, which seems consistent with the definition of hot streaks. Interestingly, hot streaks at the late career stage are observed with smaller variations in research topics despite larger teams. Team science patterns at a career's late stages seems to have a room to explore. Note that temporal dynamics of hot streaks for each field are almost consistent (Appendix), thus this is robust no matter which research field researchers belong to.

Discussion

Hot streaks are often observed in the early stage, and students and postdocs likely produce these. Scientists who write more than 80 papers throughout their careers probably publish high-impact papers with their supervisors in the early years (Li et.al. 2020), which can be explained as survival bias. Hot streaks are observed later in their careers maybe because they have obtained tenure, resulting has established track records and standings in their field. Rather than during the mid-career period when they are doing competitive activities, high-impact papers are published after settling down. It may be caused by unfettered thought to engage in creative activities, or it could be a prestige effect that increases the reputation as a major player in the field.

Figure 2. Left: Distribution of the team size. Team size is the number of authors of each paper. 13,247 papers are selected from the early hot streaks (blue line) and 9,573 papers from the late (green line). Distribution of 9,879 and 9,631 papers written by scientists without hot streaks at the early (orange line) and the late stage (red line) are also shown. Note that we exclude papers with more than 50 authors as outliers for a reasonable comparison. The inset shows the mean values of the team size with standard error. Each difference is statistically significant in Welch's t-test with a p-value less than $1e-9$. Right: Distribution of the number of topics on which scientists work during hot streaks. We evaluate 1,330 and 1,093 authors from the early and the late hot streaks, respectively. For those without hot streaks, we also compared the number of topics in ten consecutive papers for 1,000 authors each in the early and late periods. The mean numbers of topics are compared in the inset with standard error bars. Each difference is statistically significant in Welch's t-test with a p-value less than $1e-6$.

Absolute impact is a twin peak, while collective impact, which indicates the researcher's degree of attention, is constant throughout a career (Liu et.al. 2018). This suggests that the attention of mid-career researchers is due to a strong effect of shedding light on past papers in addition to the papers they produced at that time, like the boosting effect of Nobel prize winners (Mazlounian et.al. 2011). The discovery of the late hot streak implies that researchers at the end of their careers are more likely to make high-impact discoveries on their own rather than through the boosting effect. It is reasonable to the second-peak of individual publications inferring a rush to get their final remaining ideas and unpublished research out into the world (Jones et.al. 2014). This result could explain the existence of the meso-level peak of scientific creativity.

For senior researchers, it seems straightforward to handle diverse topics due to supervise their research groups. However, to make them brighter, focusing on fewer topics with many scientists might be more advantageous. Despite the composition of larger teams in the later years, the average numbers of topics are lower than in the earlier years. Typically, the number of topics is expected to increase as the team size increases, but surprisingly, it decreases. This trend is the same for those with and without hot streaks, but the senior researchers with hot streaks work on the fewest topics with the largest team sizes. Hot streaks in the latter are characterized by team formation with many scientists whose interests are common in focused themes. Such intensive resource allocation might be risky, but we can expect rewards. In addition, the

collaboration pattern (Fig.1: Right) between 0.9-1.0 shows career trends for senior scholars. Moving to the co-authors from the last probably represents the disengagement from the group supervisor or the institute leadership.

The number of topics tends to be higher in the early career years. In particular, the distribution without hot streaks has the largest ratio at 10 (Fig.2: Right). Possibly, scientists may not be aware that they are working on many topics at the early stage because topics are identified by looking back on their entire publications until the career ends.

Hot streaks exist rare at nearly 5%, but it is even rarer for that scientist's legacy to be generated in the late career stage. Can we increase this probability? Comparing the demographics of scientists who experience hot streaks in the later years of their careers with those who do not, we could obtain clues to setting the environments that promote making hot streaks happen. It is conceivable that teamwork will be more critical late in the career. However, team dynamics in the late have yet to be elucidated. The findings presented in this study may shed light on this challenging issue. From another perspective, it may help comprehend the issue more by measuring how hot streaks differ from the other types of success, such as promotion, funding, and institutional placement. We will investigate more closely in the future.

Conclusions

To clarify when hot streaks, a particularly creative period in a researcher's career, happen in what team science pattern, we examined the collaboration patterns of researchers with absolute hot streaks. First, hot streaks frequently occur in careers' early and late stages, with the dominant contributions of first authors and co-authors, respectively. Second, In the early years, researchers with hot streaks are working on smaller teams and fewer topics than those without hot streaks, whereas in the late years, they are working on larger teams and fewer topics than those without hot streaks. We elucidate that hot streaks follow different team dynamics depending on the career stages of scientists. These results help consider creative ecosystems in science or practical support for scientists at any career stage. Especially in the late stages, how do impactful scientists organize teams focusing on fewer topics with many members? To identify the meso-level team structure, we will further evaluate team freshness, co-authorship patterns, topic novelty, and diversity of topics for senior scientists with and without hot streaks.

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Appendix

As a test of the validity of the absolute impact hot streaks extracted in this study, we examined whether they shifted from exploration to exploitation in topic entropy (Appendix Fig: Left). Co-citation network clustering of each author's publication provided the topic of each papers (Zeng et.al. 2019), applying modularity maximization by Leiden method with resolution = 1 (Traag et.al. 2019). Since old papers have fewer references due to data limitations, we limited publications with more than five references in the dataset to calculate topic entropy. Appendix Fig.1 shows the average entropy $\langle H \rangle$ measured before and during the hot streaks. It clearly follows exploration to exploitation strategy, which is a unique structure around the hot streak phenomenon (Liu et.al. 2021). Subsequently, the absolute hot streak in this study is solid and verified timing in scientists' careers.

To check whether the twin peaks of the hot streak is attributed to the type of research field, the temporal change respectively colored in Appendix Fig: Right. The research field of hot streak paper is calculated from all science journal classifications (ASJC) assigned to all journals in Scopus. While having its ups and downs at different times, all research field experience both early and late hot streaks. Thus, this paper's the novel finding of twin peaks is robust regardless of the research field.

Appendix Fig. Left: The dynamics of topic entropy H surrounding the onset of a hot streak for target authors, measured through a sliding window of five publications. / Right: Relative frequency of research field's temporal patterns for hot streak authors' top 3 papers. Since all science journal classification is heterogeneously attributed to the journal, the number of papers is normalized by the total number of journals assigned to each class.